

Context-dependent phase structure in Z -diagonal unitaries detected via plaquette curvature profiles

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Higher-order diagonal interactions (involving three or more qubits) can make the effective two-qubit phase depend on spectator-qubit states, a form of context dependence that scalar benchmarks intentionally average away. Full tomographic reconstruction can in principle resolve such structure, but at a cost that scales exponentially with system size. We introduce a gauge-invariant plaquette curvature defined for each qubit pair and spectator configuration of a Z -diagonal unitary, and prove that strictly 2-local diagonal generators yield a flat curvature profile, whereas diagonal terms involving three or more qubits that include the diagnostic pair can break this flatness. The protocol estimates the curvature for each spectator context with a four-setting readout combining expectation values into complex phase factors (phasors), using only single-qubit Clifford gates and Z -basis measurement. Simulations ($n = 2-7$) demonstrate and IBM QPU experiments corroborate the scalar-versus-profile contrast: profile dispersion grows with the strength of higher-order diagonal content while context-collapsed scalar summaries remain nearly unchanged. Because spectator contexts can be sampled rather than exhaustively enumerated, measurement overhead scales with the sampling budget rather than with qubit count.

I. INTRODUCTION

Coherent, systematic Z -phase errors can accumulate in structured circuits rather than averaging out. Parasitic ZZ couplings[1, 2], cross-resonance phase residues[3], and spectator-induced frequency shifts[4] contribute phase offsets whose effective value can depend on the configuration of other qubits. When an entangling operation acquires a phase that depends on a spectator qubit's state[5], this dependence can persist across repeated layers and introduce context-dependent diagonal cross-effects.

Operationally, it is useful to view this phenomenon as a *conditional* controlled-phase: for a fixed pair (i, j) , the nonlocal phase one would associate with an ideal two-qubit CPhase gate is not necessarily a single number, but can become a function of the spectator bitstring z_{rest} . For Z -diagonal dynamics, such context dependence arises naturally from higher-weight Z -strings that include the diagnosed pair; toggling spectators changes the sign of those contributions and shifts the effective two-qubit phase. Aggregate benchmarks can therefore remain stable even when conditional phases vary, because the averaging step collapses this dependence into a single effective value.

Such effects are relevant whenever computations rely on Z -diagonal structure. In the quantum approximate optimization algorithm (QAOA)[6], coherent miscalibration in the diagonal cost-Hamiltonian gates can shift the optimization landscape. Variational eigensolvers built from diagonal entanglers[7–9] are similarly sensitive, as systematic phase offsets propagate across layers and bias energy estimates. Trotterized Hamilto-

nian simulation[10, 11] includes repeated diagonal interaction substeps in which coherent per-step errors accumulate with circuit depth rather than partially canceling. Syndrome-extraction circuits in quantum error correction contain diagonal gates whose phase errors can introduce correlated faults between data and ancilla qubits, challenging independent-error assumptions.[5, 12] Across these settings, higher-order diagonal residues—phase terms that depend on multiple spectator qubits—represent a class of coherent error whose structure is not routinely resolved by aggregate diagnostics.

Widely used characterization protocols commonly emphasize either scalable aggregate metrics or detailed reconstructions. Context-agnostic scalar benchmarks[13–16] provide efficient and SPAM-robust health checks, but they intentionally average over circuit and spectator context and therefore do not report how an effective two-qubit phase varies across spectator configurations. Tomographic reconstruction methods[17, 18] such as gate set tomography[19, 20] can in principle capture such dependence, but their measurement overhead scales exponentially with qubit count, limiting routine use beyond small systems. These complementary design goals motivate diagnostics in an intermediate regime: protocols that retain targeted structural information while remaining compatible with sampling-based experiments.

Recent work has addressed aspects of this intermediate regime. Statistical tests can detect *whether* circuit behavior depends on external context variables, returning a binary verdict and a scalar measure of distributional distance (e.g., total-variation distance or Jensen–Shannon divergence between outcome distributions obtained in different contexts)[5]. Crosstalk-detection protocols can further *localize* which subsystems interact[12]. These tools establish the presence and rough location of context dependence, but they do not retain the *functional form* of that dependence across spectator configurations—

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information that connects gate-level observations to the locality structure of the underlying error generator. The present work targets this structural layer: for a specific qubit pair, not merely whether a spectator-dependent effect exists, but how the effective nonlocal phase varies as a function of spectator state, yielding a context-resolved diagnostic whose shape encodes the spectator-parity signature of higher-weight diagonal terms.

Accordingly, the goal is not full reconstruction of the diagonal generator, but a pair-resolved screen that reports whether the effective two-qubit phase is *flat* across spectators or exhibits structured variation. Two design features are essential: the reported quantity should be invariant to local- Z “gauge” freedom, and it should be estimable from a modest number of sampled contexts without enumerating the full 2^{n-2} space.

This work introduces κ -profiles, a context-resolved diagnostic for Z -diagonal unitaries based on plaquette curvature[21, 22]. For a chosen qubit pair (i, j) , spectator configurations are sampled and the curvature κ_{ij} is estimated for each context, yielding a profile over spectator states. For diagonal unitaries generated by at most 2-local terms, κ_{ij} is independent of the spectator configuration and the profile is flat. We show that diagonal terms of weight ≥ 3 involving the diagnostic pair can break this flatness, producing context-dependent variation in the profile. The flatness condition thus connects gate-level diagnostics to the locality structure of the generating Hamiltonian: a flat profile is a necessary consequence of strictly pairwise diagonal coupling, and its violation witnesses irreducible many-body phase structure beyond the two-body level. The readout uses a four-setting phase measurement per context, requiring only single-qubit Clifford gates and Z -basis measurement in addition to the unitary under test. In controlled simulations, increasing higher-order diagonal content increases κ -profile dispersion while context-collapsed scalar summaries remain nearly unchanged. IBM QPU experiments[23–25] corroborate that this scalar-versus-profile contrast is observable under device noise. Because spectator contexts can be sampled rather than exhaustively enumerated, the measurement overhead scales with the chosen sampling budget rather than with system size.

Section II defines plaquette curvature, κ -profiles, and the four-setting estimator, with a derivation given in Appendix C. Section III specifies the controlled-injection Hamiltonian family and the experimental design shared by simulation and hardware. Section IV presents simulation results that isolate the scalar-versus-profile contrast under controlled conditions, and Section V reports hardware results together with drift-robustness checks summarized in Appendices A and B. Section VI compares κ -profiles with representative QCVV protocols and discusses scalability, application contexts, and limitations. Section VII concludes.

(A) Plaquette curvature κ

(B) Diagonal decomposition

FIG. 1. **Plaquette curvature κ isolates the nonlocal content of a two-qubit Z -diagonal unitary.** (a) The alternating phase sum $\kappa \equiv \phi_{00} + \phi_{11} - \phi_{01} - \phi_{10} \pmod{2\pi}$ is invariant under global and single-qubit Z phases. (b) Any two-qubit diagonal unitary factorizes (up to global phase) as $U = e^{i\gamma}(D_i \otimes D_j) \text{CPhase}(\kappa)$; hence $\kappa \equiv 0 \pmod{2\pi}$ iff U is local-diagonal.

II. PRELIMINARIES

A. Plaquette curvature κ

Consider a two-qubit Z -diagonal unitary

$$U = \text{diag}(e^{i\phi_{00}}, e^{i\phi_{01}}, e^{i\phi_{10}}, e^{i\phi_{11}}), \quad (1)$$

where each diagonal phase $\phi_{ab} \in \mathbb{R}$ is defined modulo 2π . The four phases can be visualized as vertices of a square in the two-qubit state space (Fig. 1a).

We define the *plaquette curvature* as the alternating sum

$$\kappa \equiv \phi_{00} + \phi_{11} - \phi_{01} - \phi_{10} \pmod{2\pi}. \quad (2)$$

Geometrically, κ measures the flux through the plaquette formed by the four computational basis states under

single-bit flips.[21, 22] The plaquette terminology is borrowed by structural analogy: the four basis states form a discrete cycle under single-bit flips, and κ plays the role of a holonomy around this cycle; no gauge field or continuum limit is implied. Only the curvature phasor $e^{i\kappa}$ is branch-free; any real representative $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}$ is defined modulo 2π .

a. Mixed second-difference viewpoint. Equation (2) can also be read as a discrete mixed second difference of the phase field on the $\{0, 1\}^2$ plaquette: $\kappa = \Delta_i \Delta_j \phi$. From this perspective, any contribution that depends on at most one plaquette direction has zero mixed difference, which is precisely the cancellation shown in Eq. (3). In the Ising-type generator of Eq. (7), the surviving term for pair (i, j) is $b_{ij} Z_i Z_j$, and the factor of 4 in Eq. (8) reflects that $Z_i Z_j$ takes values ± 1 : the alternating sum adds the two “+1” vertices and subtracts the two “−1” vertices, yielding $4b_{ij} \pmod{2\pi}$.

b. Gauge invariance. The curvature κ is invariant under global phase shifts and independent single-qubit Z rotations. Specifically, if we transform $\phi_{ab} \mapsto \phi_{ab} + \gamma + \alpha_a + \beta_b$ for arbitrary $\gamma, \alpha_0, \alpha_1, \beta_0, \beta_1 \in \mathbb{R}$, then

$$\kappa' = \kappa + (\alpha_0 - \alpha_1 - \alpha_0 + \alpha_1) + (\beta_0 - \beta_0 - \beta_1 + \beta_1) = \kappa. \quad (3)$$

Thus κ isolates the genuinely two-qubit content of the diagonal, filtering out local- Z degrees of freedom.

c. Diagonal decomposition. Any two-qubit diagonal unitary admits the factorization[26]

$$U = e^{i\gamma} (D_i \otimes D_j) \cdot \text{CPhase}(\kappa), \quad (4)$$

where D_i, D_j are single-qubit diagonal unitaries and $\text{CPhase}(\kappa) := \text{diag}(1, 1, 1, e^{i\kappa})$ is the controlled-phase gate (Fig. 1b). This decomposition shows that κ is the unique nonlocal parameter of a two-qubit diagonal gate.

d. Locality criterion. The decomposition (4) implies an equivalence:

$$\kappa \equiv 0 \pmod{2\pi} \iff U \text{ is local-diagonal.} \quad (5)$$

A diagonal unitary with $\kappa = 0$ can be written as a product of single-qubit Z gates (up to global phase) and is non-entangling; conversely, any nonzero κ witnesses irreducible two-qubit nonlocal diagonal content. This two-qubit invariant serves as the building block for the context-resolved diagnostic developed in the following sections.

B. κ -profiles for $n \geq 3$

For systems with three or more qubits, the curvature κ_{ij} depends on the configuration of the remaining qubits. Consider an n -qubit Z -diagonal unitary $U = \text{diag}(e^{i\phi(z)})$ with $z \in \{0, 1\}^n$. Fix a diagnostic pair (i, j) and let $z_{\text{rest}} \in \{0, 1\}^{n-2}$ denote the bitstring of the *spectator* qubits (all qubits except i and j). Define $z^{ab}(z_{\text{rest}})$ as the n -bit string with bits $(z_i, z_j) = (a, b)$ and spectator

bits equal to z_{rest} . The plaquette curvature at context z_{rest} is then

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}}) = & \phi(z^{00}) + \phi(z^{11}) \\ & - \phi(z^{01}) - \phi(z^{10}) \pmod{2\pi}, \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

in direct analogy with the two-qubit definition (2). As in the two-qubit case, $\kappa_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}})$ is invariant under global phase and static single-qubit Z rotations on any qubit (including spectators), since such terms contribute equally to all four plaquette vertices and cancel in the alternating sum. The κ -profile for pair (i, j) is the function $z_{\text{rest}} \mapsto \kappa_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}})$ over all 2^{n-2} spectator configurations.

1. Flatness under 2-local structure.

A central theoretical result is that purely 2-local diagonal unitaries produce flat κ -profiles. Suppose the diagonal phase field arises from an Ising-type generator,

$$U = \exp\left(i \sum_k a_k Z_k + i \sum_{k < \ell} b_{k\ell} Z_k Z_\ell\right). \quad (7)$$

Then for any pair (i, j) , the curvature is independent of the spectator configuration:

$$\kappa_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}}) \equiv 4b_{ij} \pmod{2\pi} \quad \text{for all } z_{\text{rest}}. \quad (8)$$

The proof follows from the alternating-sum structure of (6): every 1-local term cancels because it depends on at most one plaquette direction, and every 2-local term $Z_k Z_\ell$ cancels unless $\{k, \ell\} = \{i, j\}$. Thus a flat κ -profile is the expected baseline for systems with only pairwise diagonal couplings. The alternating-sum identity underlying this result is elementary; its diagnostic value lies in connecting a gate-level observable— κ -profile flatness, extracted from black-box measurement statistics via the four-setting readout of Section IID—to a generator-level structural property (interaction locality).

a. Non-converse. Equation (8) is one-directional: flatness does not certify the absence of higher-weight terms, since such terms can cancel from κ_{ij} if they exclude either i or j , or (in special cases) wrap to a constant modulo 2π . We therefore treat a flat profile as a null result for this pair, whereas non-flatness is an informative fingerprint.

2. Context dependence from higher-order terms.

When diagonal terms of weight three or higher are present, the κ -profile can become context-dependent. Consider a minimal example with $n = 3$ qubits and generator $H = \gamma Z_0 Z_1 + \eta Z_0 Z_1 Z_2$. For the diagnostic pair $(0, 1)$, the sole spectator is qubit 2. Using the sign convention $s_k := (-1)^{z_k}$, [27] direct calculation gives

$$\kappa_{01}(z_2) = 4\gamma + 4\eta s_2 \pmod{2\pi}. \quad (9)$$

When $z_2 = 0$ (so $s_2 = +1$) the curvature is $4(\gamma + \eta)$; when $z_2 = 1$ (so $s_2 = -1$) it shifts to $4(\gamma - \eta)$. The spectator qubit acts as a *switch*: its state modulates the effective two-body phase between qubits 0 and 1. This switching mechanism generalizes to higher weights—a weight- w term Z_S with $\{i, j\} \subset S$ contributes to κ_{ij} with a sign that depends on the parity $\prod_{k \in S \setminus \{i, j\}} s_k$ of the remaining spectator bits in S .

In general, κ_{ij} can be read as the sum of all Z -string coefficients whose support includes both i and j , each weighted by a spectator-parity factor that depends on the context z_{rest} . A higher-weight term Z_S is therefore invisible to κ_{ij} whenever S does not contain the diagnostic pair, even if it acts on qubits that are spectators of (i, j) . Conversely, every term that does contain $\{i, j\}$ leaves a context-dependent imprint whose sign flips with the parity of the remaining bits in S .

a. Diagnostic interpretation. A non-flat κ -profile serves as a *structural fingerprint* indicating the presence of diagonal cross-effects beyond pairwise couplings. Note that κ -profiles provide a fingerprint for screening, not identification: profile non-flatness is consistent with higher-order diagonal terms, but could also arise from out-of-model effects such as multi-setting drift or non-diagonal leakage.[5, 28] The distinction between structural signal and measurement artifacts is addressed through quality diagnostics and control experiments in subsequent sections.

C. Scalar summaries and their limitations

In practice, we obtain context-resolved curvature estimates $\hat{\kappa}_{ij}(c)$ via the four-setting readout described in Section IID. Given these estimates, many characterization workflows compress the full κ -profile into a single scalar. Two common conventions are *context averaging* and *spectator fixing*.

a. Context-averaged effective phase. Averaging the curvature phasor over all spectator configurations yields the *effective curvature*

$$\hat{\kappa}_{ij}^{\text{eff}} := \arg\left(\frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}|} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} e^{i\hat{\kappa}_{ij}(c)}\right), \quad (10)$$

where \mathcal{C} denotes the set of sampled contexts. This circular mean is the natural point estimator under a flat-profile assumption: if $\kappa_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}})$ is constant, then $\hat{\kappa}_{ij}^{\text{eff}}$ recovers that constant (up to statistical noise).

b. Fixed-spectator convention. An alternative is to fix the spectators to a canonical state, typically $z_{\text{rest}} = 0 \cdots 0$, and report only $\hat{\kappa}_{ij}(0 \cdots 0)$. This convention avoids averaging altogether but probes only a single point of the profile.

FIG. 2. **Four-setting phasor κ readout.** For a Z -diagonal unitary U , fix a diagnostic pair (i, j) and spectator context $|z_{\text{rest}}\rangle$. Four settings $(x, s) \in \{0, 1\}^2$ yield $m_{x,s} := \langle Z_j \rangle$, forming phasors $u_a := m_{0,0} + i m_{0,1}$ and $u_b := m_{1,0} + i m_{1,1}$. The estimator $\hat{\kappa}_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}}) = \text{Arg}(u_a \bar{u}_b)$ targets the plaquette curvature.

1. Information loss under non-flat profiles.

Both scalar conventions perform well when the underlying κ -profile is flat: the effective phase equals the common value, and any parked context is representative. This is not a flaw; such scalars are optimized for efficient, context-agnostic screening and therefore intentionally compress away spectator dependence.[13, 14, 29] However, when the profile exhibits context dependence, these scalars can obscure the very structure we aim to detect. Consider the three-qubit example of Eq. (9): the curvature oscillates between $4(\gamma + \eta)$ and $4(\gamma - \eta)$ as z_2 varies. If $|\eta|$ is sufficiently small (so that the phasor mean does not wrap), the context-averaged $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ remains close to 4γ —nearly unchanged from the $\eta = 0$ baseline—even though the profile dispersion has increased. The scalar compresses away the context-dependent structure.

This motivates the κ -profile as the primary diagnostic object: rather than collapsing to a single number, we retain the full map $z_{\text{rest}} \mapsto \kappa_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}})$ and quantify its dispersion. The contrast between scalar stability and profile variability is demonstrated empirically in Section IV C.

D. Four-setting phasor readout

The plaquette curvature κ is not directly observable; it must be inferred from measurement statistics. We now describe a hardware-friendly protocol that extracts $\kappa_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}})$ using only single-qubit Clifford gates and Z -basis measurements, with black-box access to the diagonal unitary U .

a. Phase difference decomposition. The curvature can be written as a difference of two phase differences:

$$\kappa = a - b, \quad (11)$$

where $a := \phi(z^{00}) - \phi(z^{01})$ and $b := \phi(z^{10}) - \phi(z^{11})$. Each of a and b is a relative phase between two computational basis states differing only in qubit j . The key observation is that such relative phases can be converted

into measurable expectation values via Hadamard and S -gate rotations on qubit j . [26, 30]

b. Circuit structure. Figure 2 depicts the four-setting circuit. For a fixed diagnostic pair (i, j) and spectator context $|z_{\text{rest}}\rangle$, we prepare qubit i in state $X^x|0\rangle$ and qubit j in $H|0\rangle = |+\rangle$, apply U , then measure qubit j in a rotated basis determined by gates before the final Z measurement. The Hadamard on qubit j places it on the equatorial plane, and the optional S gate selects the measurement quadrature (X versus Y), yielding cosine and sine components of the acquired phase. The two binary parameters $(x, s) \in \{0, 1\}^2$ define four circuit settings, each yielding an expectation value $m_{x,s} := \langle Z_j \rangle$. In the ideal (noiseless) limit, these are:

$$\begin{aligned} m_{0,0} &= \cos a, & m_{0,1} &= \sin a, \\ m_{1,0} &= \cos b, & m_{1,1} &= \sin b. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The detailed derivation is given in Appendix C.

c. Phasor estimator. We combine the four expectation values into two complex phasors,

$$u_a := m_{0,0} + i m_{0,1}, \quad u_b := m_{1,0} + i m_{1,1}, \quad (13)$$

which equal e^{ia} and e^{ib} respectively in the noiseless limit. The curvature estimate is then

$$\hat{\kappa}_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}}) = \text{Arg}(u_a \bar{u}_b), \quad (14)$$

where $\text{Arg}(\cdot) \in (-\pi, \pi]$ denotes the principal argument. This phasor-based estimator is robust to 2π wrapping; even when $|a|$ or $|b|$ individually exceeds π , the product $u_a \bar{u}_b = e^{i(a-b)} = e^{i\kappa}$ remains well-defined.

d. Resource scaling. Each context requires four circuit settings. For M sampled contexts and P diagnostic pairs, the total circuit count is $4MP$; with N shots per setting, the total shot count is $4MPN$.

e. Quality diagnostic. In the ideal (noiseless) case, $|u_a| = |u_b| = 1$. Noise sources such as SPAM errors, dephasing, and readout infidelity reduce these amplitudes. We define the *minimum phasor amplitude*

$$\text{amp}_{\min} := \min(|u_a|, |u_b|) \quad (15)$$

as a per-context quality diagnostic. A low amp_{\min} indicates that the corresponding $\hat{\kappa}$ estimate may be unreliable; we report this metric alongside all curvature measurements.

f. Drift sensitivity. Because the four settings are measured in separate circuit executions, time-varying drift can introduce bias. [28] As a precaution, we employ *interleaved scheduling*: the four settings are executed in short repeating cycles, rather than in sequential blocks. The drift model is presented in Section III D; a robustness check comparing scheduling strategies is reported in Appendix A.

E. Profile dispersion metric

To quantify context dependence in a κ -profile, we use circular statistics that respect the angular nature of phase

data. [31, 32]

a. Circular dispersion. For a set of curvature estimates $\{\hat{\kappa}_{ij}(c)\}_{c \in \mathcal{C}}$ over contexts \mathcal{C} , define the *mean resultant phasor*

$$\bar{z}_{ij} := \frac{1}{|\mathcal{C}|} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} e^{i\hat{\kappa}_{ij}(c)}. \quad (16)$$

This is the same complex average used to define the effective curvature $\hat{\kappa}_{ij}^{\text{eff}} = \arg(\bar{z}_{ij})$ in Section II C; its magnitude $R_{ij} := |\bar{z}_{ij}|$ measures the concentration of phasors around the circular mean. When all phasors are identical, $R_{ij} = 1$; when they are uniformly spread around the circle, $R_{ij} \rightarrow 0$. The *circular dispersion* is defined as

$$V_{ij}^{\text{circ}} := 1 - R_{ij}. \quad (17)$$

A flat κ -profile yields $V_{ij}^{\text{circ}} \approx 0$ (up to shot noise), while context-dependent structure produces $V_{ij}^{\text{circ}} > 0$.

b. Paired reporting with quality diagnostic. Elevated V_{ij}^{circ} can arise from two distinct sources: genuine context dependence in the underlying κ -profile, or degraded measurement quality (e.g., low phasor amplitudes due to noise). To distinguish these, we report V_{ij}^{circ} alongside the mean or minimum amp_{\min} across contexts. If V_{ij}^{circ} is elevated while amp_{\min} remains high, the data are consistent with structural non-flatness rather than pure visibility loss; other potential sources such as multi-setting drift are addressed via scheduling and control strategies in subsequent sections. This paired reporting is maintained throughout the simulation and hardware results that follow.

III. METHODS

This section describes the experimental design shared by both simulation and hardware experiments. The four-setting phasor readout protocol was introduced in Section II D; here we specify the test Hamiltonians, graph construction, context enumeration, and drift mitigation strategies.

A. Model Hamiltonian and η_3 injection sweep

To validate the diagnostic capabilities of κ -profiles, we construct families of Z -diagonal unitaries with controllable higher-order content. Building on the Ising-type structure in Eq. (7), we consider Hamiltonians of the form

$$H = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} \alpha_{ij} Z_i Z_j + \eta_3 \cdot \sum_{(i,j,k) \in T_{01}} \beta_{ijk} Z_i Z_j Z_k, \quad (18)$$

where E denotes the set of edges (2-local couplings) and T_{01} denotes the set of 3-local terms that include the diagnostic pair $(0, 1)$. The test unitary is then $U = \exp(iH)$.

The coefficients α_{ij} and β_{ijk} are generated from fixed random seeds for reproducibility. In the reported experiments, all 2-local couplings share a common scale, while the weight-3 coefficients are zero-mean random variables whose overall magnitude is controlled by η_3 .

a. Commuting structure and black-box access. All terms in Eq. (18) are Pauli- Z strings and therefore commute, so $U = \exp(iH)$ is exactly Z -diagonal and the model family carries no Trotterization error. In simulation we apply U directly as a diagonal phase map, whereas on hardware the same diagonal action is realized by a compiled circuit. The κ -profile protocol treats U as a black box: only the input–output statistics under single-qubit Clifford wrappers are used, so the diagnostic remains well-defined even when the gate-level implementation or compiler choices vary.

b. The η_3 parameter. The scalar $\eta_3 \in [0, 1]$ controls the strength of 3-local terms relative to the 2-local baseline. The parameter η_3 is *not* a device parameter or a physical noise strength; it is a *control parameter* that defines a family of controlled test cases. When $\eta_3 = 0$, the Hamiltonian is purely 2-local, and by the flatness result of Eq. (8), the κ -profile for any pair should be context-independent; this configuration serves as the *2-local baseline*, establishing the measurement floor under ideal conditions. When $\eta_3 > 0$, nonzero 3-local content is injected, and following the mechanism described in Section II B, spectator qubits act as switches that modulate the effective two-body coupling, producing context-dependent κ -profiles; these configurations serve as the *injected perturbation family*, with increasing η_3 producing progressively stronger context dependence. We sweep $\eta_3 \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2\}$ throughout both simulation and hardware experiments. This range spans from the 2-local baseline ($\eta_3 = 0$) to progressively stronger injected weight-3 perturbations ($\eta_3 = 0.1, 0.2$), enabling a controlled characterization of the diagnostic sensitivity.

c. Selective 3-local injection. A key design choice is that 3-local terms are injected *only* for strings containing the diagnostic pair $(0, 1)$; that is, terms of the form $(0, 1, k)$ with $k \notin \{0, 1\}$. In practice, only a subset of such terms is injected based on graph-distance and sparsity rules. This selective injection isolates the variable of interest: other pairs may still carry baseline 2-local ZZ couplings, but only the diagnostic pair is exposed to injected weight-3 terms. As shown in Section III B, this enables the construction of *connected-flat control* pairs—pairs with nonzero ZZ coupling but excluded from 3-local injection—whose κ -profiles remain flat even as η_3 increases, providing an internal consistency check.

d. Connection to the theoretical framework. The construction (18) generalizes the three-qubit example of Eq. (9), which corresponds to the special case $n = 3$ with a single 2-local coefficient $\gamma \equiv \alpha_{01}$ and a single 3-local coefficient $\eta \equiv \eta_3 \beta_{012}$. The general Hamiltonian extends this structure to arbitrary qubit counts and graph topologies while preserving the same diagnostic logic: 2-local terms produce flat κ -profiles, and 3-local terms

(when present) introduce context dependence through the spectator-switch mechanism identified in Section II B.

B. Graph structure and pair selection

The diagnostic pair $(0, 1)$ is fixed throughout all experiments; the remaining qubits are added incrementally to form a nested family of graphs $G_2 \subset G_3 \subset \dots \subset G_n$. To ensure cross- n comparability, we enforce prefix stability: coefficients for existing edges and terms are deterministic functions of a fixed seed and the term indices, so increasing n only appends new terms without altering previously defined ones.

a. Graph growth via BFS shells. Starting from the diagnostic edge $(0, 1)$, we expand the graph by breadth-first search (BFS): qubits at graph distance 1 from $\{0, 1\}$ are added first, then distance 2, and so on. Within each shell, ties are broken deterministically by a fixed coordinate ordering. In simulation, we use a centered-growth layout on a fixed grid so that the seed edge $(0, 1)$ remains near the grid center as n increases, avoiding boundary artifacts. For each n , the induced subgraph G_n on the first n qubits defines the connectivity, and every edge in G_n carries a 2-local ZZ coupling. We sweep $n \in \{2, 3, \dots, 7\}$, which at $n = 7$ yields $2^{n-2} = 32$ spectator contexts for exhaustive enumeration.

b. Signal and control pairs. A key element of our experimental design is the use of *control pairs* that share the same baseline structure as the signal pair but are excluded from 3-local injection. Here “connected” means that (u, v) is an edge of G_n , i.e., it carries a baseline ZZ coupling. Recall from Section III A that all injected weight-3 terms have the form $Z_0 Z_1 Z_k$, containing the diagnostic pair $(0, 1)$. Because the κ -profile for a pair (u, v) acquires context dependence only when at least one higher-weight term contains *both* u and v (the spectator-switch mechanism of Section II B), we select the control pair as a connected edge that is not jointly contained in any injected weight-3 term. By this cancellation argument, such a pair exhibits a context-independent κ -profile regardless of η_3 .

This construction realizes an *isolated-variable design*: both signal and control pairs are connected (nonzero ZZ), but only the signal pair is affected by the η_3 perturbation. If κ -profile dispersion grows with η_3 for the signal pair while remaining flat for the control pair, we obtain evidence that the observed context dependence arises from the injected 3-local content rather than from measurement artifacts or baseline graph structure.

c. Topology-dependent control pair selection. The specific control pair depends on the underlying graph topology: in simulation, we use a two-dimensional grid and select $(2, 3)$ as the control pair; on hardware (IBM heavy-hex topology[25]), coupling constraints lead to a different pair, $(1, 4)$. Despite differing indices, both pairs satisfy the same *role*: connected via ZZ but excluded from 3-local injection. In simulation, the control pair

(2, 3) becomes available at $n \geq 4$; on the hardware topology, the sparser heavy-hex connectivity delays availability of a connected control pair to $n \geq 5$. For smaller n , only the signal pair is measured.

C. Context encoding and enumeration

For a diagnostic pair (i, j) in an n -qubit system, the spectator configuration $z_{\text{rest}} \in \{0, 1\}^{n-2}$ determines which plaquette is probed. To ensure reproducibility and consistent indexing across experiments, we adopt a fixed encoding convention.

a. Integer encoding. We represent each spectator configuration as an integer $z_{\text{rest}}^{\text{int}} \in \{0, 1, \dots, 2^{n-2} - 1\}$ using least-significant-bit-first (LSB) ordering. Concretely, after removing qubits i and j , the remaining qubits are relabeled $0, 1, \dots, n-3$ in ascending order of their original indices; the integer encoding is then

$$z_{\text{rest}}^{\text{int}} = \sum_{m=0}^{n-3} z_m \cdot 2^m, \quad (19)$$

where $z_m \in \{0, 1\}$ is the state of the m -th relabeled spectator qubit. For example, with diagnostic pair $(0, 1)$ and $n = 7$, the spectators are qubits $\{2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$, and $z_{\text{rest}}^{\text{int}} = z_2 \cdot 2^0 + z_3 \cdot 2^1 + z_4 \cdot 2^2 + z_5 \cdot 2^3 + z_6 \cdot 2^4$. This convention is fixed throughout all experiments and reported data.

b. Exhaustive enumeration. For the system sizes considered here ($n \leq 7$), the number of spectator contexts is at most $2^{n-2} = 32$, which permits exhaustive enumeration. We measure all 2^{n-2} contexts for each diagnostic pair, eliminating sampling variance and enabling direct visualization of the full κ -profile.

c. Scaling to larger systems. For n beyond the exhaustive regime, random sampling of contexts provides a practical alternative. The circular dispersion V_{circ} (Section II E) admits a consistent estimator from uniformly sampled contexts, with variance scaling as $O(1/M)$ where M is the number of sampled contexts—independent of n . [31, 32] This sampling-based design ensures that the experimental overhead scales with the desired statistical precision rather than with qubit count, a property we revisit in Section VI B.

D. Drift mitigation

The four-setting phasor readout (Section II D) requires combining expectation values from separate circuit executions. If the effective measurement frame drifts between settings, the resulting bias can corrupt the curvature estimate. [28] We adopt several design choices to mitigate this risk.

a. Interleaved scheduling. Rather than executing all shots for one setting before moving to the next (blocked

scheduling), we interleave the four settings: measurements for different settings are executed in short cycles, so that any slow drift affects all settings comparably. In a minimal equatorial-frame drift model, the phasor estimator behaves as $\hat{\Pi} \approx e^{i(\kappa+\Delta)}$, where $\Delta := \delta_a - \delta_b$ is the difference between effective phase offsets experienced by the two setting pairs. The mean-squared error decomposes as $\text{MSE}(\hat{\kappa}) \approx \Delta^2 + O(1/N)$; unlike shot noise, drift-induced bias does not vanish with increasing shot count N . Interleaved scheduling aims to reduce $|\Delta|$ by ensuring that both setting pairs experience similar drift within each short randomized cycle; it mitigates but does not eliminate drift-induced bias. A robustness check comparing interleaved and blocked scheduling is presented in Appendix A.

b. Paired signal-control measurement. Signal and control pairs are measured within the same experimental session under identical conditions. Because both pairs experience the same drift environment, a differential comparison—signal dispersion increasing with η_3 while control remains flat—provides evidence that observed trends arise from injected structure rather than from session-specific artifacts.

c. Quality diagnostic. As introduced in Section II D, we report the minimum phasor amplitude amp_{min} alongside every curvature estimate. Drift and other noise sources reduce phasor amplitude; elevated V_{circ} accompanied by stable amp_{min} is consistent with structural context dependence, whereas degraded amp_{min} signals potential measurement-quality issues. This paired reporting is maintained throughout all results.

d. Uncertainty quantification. For simulation results, we report 95% confidence intervals via trial-level bootstrap over independent random instances. [33, 34] For hardware (QPU) data, we report 95% confidence intervals via shot-level bootstrap from raw measurement counts. When comparing signal and control pairs, bootstrap resampling is performed in a paired fashion to preserve within-session correlations.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section presents simulation results demonstrating the diagnostic capabilities of κ -profiles under controlled conditions. We first summarize the experimental setup, then examine how the circular dispersion V_{circ} [31, 32] evolves with system size and injected 3-local strength, and finally demonstrate the central finding: scalar summaries can remain nearly constant while the underlying κ -profile exhibits substantial context dependence.

A. Setup overview

Following Section III, we simulate the four-setting phasor κ readout on a 3×3 grid with centered-growth indexing (BFS shells anchored at the diagnostic edge $(0, 1)$).

We sweep $n \in \{2, 3, \dots, 7\}$ and exhaustively enumerate all 2^{n-2} spectator contexts (32 at $n = 7$), using the LSB-first encoding convention of Section III C. A fixed-seed Hamiltonian instance is generated following the prefix-stable design of Section III B, and the 3-local injection strength is swept over $\eta_3 \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2\}$: $\eta_3 = 0$ serves as the 2-local baseline (flat profile expected), while $\eta_3 > 0$ provides injected perturbations with progressively stronger context dependence. We measure the signal pair $(0, 1)$, which is affected by injected weight-3 terms, and for $n \geq 4$ the control pair $(2, 3)$, which carries a baseline ZZ coupling but is excluded from 3-local injection. Each setting uses $N = 2048$ shots with binomial sampling; in addition, we include the minimal multi-setting drift model[28] described in Section III D ($\sigma = 0.02$ rad). We perform 20 independent trials and report 95% confidence intervals via trial-level bootstrap[33, 34] for V_{circ} , always alongside the phasor quality diagnostic amp_{min} . Across trials, the Hamiltonian coefficients are held fixed; only the shot noise and drift realizations are resampled. All settings are executed with interleaved scheduling.

Holding the Hamiltonian coefficients fixed across trials isolates the estimator variability attributable to finite sampling and multi-setting drift, rather than mixing in instance-to-instance variation in the underlying profile. The resulting confidence intervals therefore represent repeatability for a fixed diagonal unitary under comparable noise conditions. This choice also makes the η_3 sweep interpretable as a controlled sensitivity test on a single phase landscape, mirroring the way a hardware experiment would probe one compiled circuit at different injected strengths.

B. Dispersion scaling with system size

Figure 3 summarizes the η_3 sweep across system sizes $n = 2-7$. Panel A shows the κ -profile dispersion V_{circ} as a function of n for both the signal pair $(0, 1)$ and the control pair $(2, 3)$. For $n = 2$, there are no spectators (a single context), so V_{circ} is identically zero by definition.

For the baseline ($\eta_3 = 0$), the signal pair exhibits V_{circ} values indistinguishable from the measurement floor across all n , consistent with the flatness result of Section II B: a purely 2-local Hamiltonian produces context-independent κ -profiles. As η_3 increases, the signal pair shows progressively larger dispersion, with clear separation between the $\eta_3 = 0.1$ and $\eta_3 = 0.2$ curves emerging at $n \geq 3$. The control pair $(2, 3)$, which carries a baseline ZZ coupling but is excluded from 3-local injection, remains flat regardless of η_3 —consistent with the hypothesis that the observed dispersion arises from the injected weight-3 content in this controlled model family, rather than from artifacts of graph growth or measurement protocol.

The dispersion curves plateau at larger n rather than growing indefinitely. This saturation reflects the locality structure of the injected terms: each 3-local term $Z_0 Z_1 Z_k$

FIG. 3. **Simulation η_3 sweep** ($n = 2-7$). Signal pair $(0, 1)$ (filled circles) and control pair $(2, 3)$ (open squares; $n \geq 4$) measured for $\eta_3 \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2\}$. (A) κ -profile dispersion V_{circ} versus n ; error bars are 95% trial-bootstrap CIs. (B) Phasor quality amp_{min} ; whiskers extend to the 10th percentile. Signal pair shows η_3 -dependent non-flatness while the control pair remains flat. ($\eta_3 = 0$: 2-local baseline; $\eta_3 > 0$: injected perturbation); plateaus reflect locality-limited spectator influence, not method failure.

affects the κ -profile only when spectator k is toggled, and the number of such terms is bounded by the graph neighborhood of the diagnostic pair, following the distance-based injection rules of Section III A. The plateau is thus a consequence of the finite-range spectator influence, not a limitation of the diagnostic method.

Panel B reports the phasor quality diagnostic amp_{min} over the same sweep. Values remain near unity for both pairs across all n and η_3 settings, confirming high interference contrast throughout the sweep.

C. Scalar summaries versus full profiles

Figure 3 establishes that κ -profile dispersion grows with η_3 for the signal pair. We now ask a sharper question: does this growth manifest in the context-collapsed scalar $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}} = \arg\langle e^{i\hat{\kappa}} \rangle$, or is it visible only in the full profile?

FIG. 4. **Simulated κ -profiles at $n = 7$: scalar summaries can mask context dependence.** Rows: $\eta_3 \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2\}$; columns: signal (0, 1) (A,C,E) vs. control pair (2, 3) (B,D,F). Each panel shows $\hat{\kappa}(z_{\text{rest}})$ (markers, left axis) and amp_{min} (dashed, right axis) across all $2^{n-2} = 32$ contexts. Dotted line: context-collapsed $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}} = \arg\langle e^{i\hat{\kappa}} \rangle$; right-margin bar: κ -profile spread $(q_{10}-q_{90})$ of wrapped deviations $\text{Arg}(e^{i(\hat{\kappa}-\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}})})$. As η_3 increases, $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ stays nearly constant while the signal profile fluctuation grows; the control remains flat.

Figure 4 displays the complete κ -profile at $n = 7$ for both signal and control pairs across the η_3 sweep. Each panel plots $\hat{\kappa}(z_{\text{rest}})$ for all 32 spectator contexts, with the scalar summary $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ shown as a horizontal dotted line and the profile spread $(q_{10}-q_{90})$ indicated by a right-margin bar. The phasor quality amp_{min} is overlaid on the right axis.

This separation between a stable circular-mean an-

gle and a growing spread is expected when context-dependent deviations are approximately balanced around a common direction: the mean phasor angle can remain pinned while its length decreases. In that regime, $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ is insensitive to widening conditional structure, whereas V_{circ} and the spread bar respond directly to the broadening of the empirical phase distribution. Figure 4 makes this geometry explicit by placing the scalar baseline and

dispersion marker in the same panels.

The key observation is the contrast between scalar and profile behavior. For this fixed Hamiltonian instance, $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ remains nearly constant across $\eta_3 \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2\}$ —a context-collapsed scalar would suggest little has changed. Yet the profile tells a different story: fluctuations around the scalar baseline grow substantially as η_3 increases, with the spread bar widening from Panel A to Panel E. In contrast, the control pair (right column) maintains a flat profile throughout, with both the scalar and the spread remaining stable.

This is the central observation: conventional scalar screening—whether by context-collapsing or spectator fixing—can hide context-dependent diagonal cross-effects that κ -profiles reveal.[5, 29] A protocol that reports only $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ would conclude that the signal pair is well-characterized by a single number, missing the context-dependent fluctuations visible in the full profile. The uniformly high amp_{min} values across all panels rule out visibility loss as a confound.

Taken together, Fig. 4 motivates reporting κ as a context-resolved object rather than as a single number. In particular, $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ is a natural scalar baseline (phasor-mean angle), but its stability can coexist with a growing profile spread as η_3 increases. Equivalently, $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ collapses the profile onto a single direction in the complex plane; dispersion statistics then quantify how much context dependence is being averaged away by that collapse. This distinction matters operationally: a non-flat profile is a structural fingerprint of spectator-dependent diagonal cross-effects involving the diagnosed pair, whereas amp_{min} guards against mistaking low-visibility data for structure. Section V repeats the same figure format and paired signal/control design on a superconducting device, testing whether the scalar-versus-profile contrast and the monotonic η_3 -dependent dispersion trend remain observable under device noise.

Figure 6 in Section V C repeats the same analysis on QPU data, echoing the scalar-versus-profile contrast demonstrated here.

V. QPU CORROBORATION

A. Dispersion scaling on hardware

This section presents hardware results on IBM `ibm_fez` that test whether the simulation findings of Section IV are reproducible under device noise. The QPU experiments test whether the simulation trends are reproducible under realistic device noise; the goal is observability, not quantitative model matching.

B. Setup

The hardware experiments follow the same η_3 injection framework as the simulations, with adaptations

FIG. 5. **QPU corroboration of the η_3 injection sweep on `ibm_fez`.** Signal pair (0, 1) (filled circles) and control pair (1, 4) (open squares) measured for $\eta_3 \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2\}$. **(A)** κ -profile dispersion V_{circ} versus n ; error bars are 95% bootstrap CIs. **(B)** Phasor quality amp_{min} ; whiskers extend to the 10th percentile. The signal shows η_3 -dependent dispersion while the control remains near the floor. Control-pair data start at $n = 5$ due to hardware coupling; simulation provides full n -sweep evidence.

for device connectivity. We execute all circuits on `ibm_fez`[23, 24], embedding the signal (diagnostic) pair (0, 1) at physical qubits 3 and 16; these serve as the BFS root from which the remaining qubits are added following the nested growth design of Section III B. The control pair is (1, 4)—a pair that carries a baseline ZZ coupling but is excluded from 3-local injection, satisfying the same role as the simulation control (2, 3). Due to heavy-hex coupling constraints[25], the control pair becomes available only at $n \geq 5$; for smaller n , only the signal pair is measured. We sweep $n \in \{2, 3, \dots, 7\}$ and $\eta_3 \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2\}$, exhaustively enumerating all 2^{n-2} spectator contexts (up to 32 at $n = 7$) using the LSB-first encoding of Section III C. Each setting uses $N = 2048$ shots with interleaved scheduling, and signal–control pairs are measured within the same experimental session to minimize drift differences[28] and enable paired comparisons (Section III D). We report 95% confidence intervals via shot-level bootstrap[33, 34] and always present the pha-

FIG. 6. **QPU echo of the scalar-versus-profile contrast on `ibm_fez` ($n = 7$).** Rows: $\eta_3 \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2\}$; columns: signal (0, 1) (A,C,E) vs. control pair (1, 4) (B,D,F). Each panel shows $\hat{\kappa}(z_{\text{rest}})$ (markers, left axis) and amp_{min} (dashed, right axis) across all $2^{n-2} = 32$ contexts. Dotted line: context-collapsed $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}} = \arg\langle e^{i\hat{\kappa}} \rangle$; right-margin bar: κ -profile spread ($q_{10} - q_{00}$). As η_3 increases, $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ stays nearly constant while the signal profile fluctuation grows; the control remains flat. Control pair differs from simulation due to device connectivity constraints, but the role is identical: a connected pair excluded from 3-local injection.

quality diagnostic amp_{min} alongside dispersion metrics.

In what follows, we first report the η_3 -dependent dispersion trend (Fig. 5), and then echo the scalar-versus-profile contrast at $n = 7$ using the same figure format as Fig. 4 (Fig. 6).

Figure 5 summarizes the η_3 sweep on `ibm_fez`, echoing

the simulation analysis of Fig. 3. Panel A shows the κ -profile dispersion V_{circ} [31, 32] as a function of n for both the signal pair (0, 1) and the control pair (1, 4). As in simulation, $n = 2$ yields a single context and hence $V_{\text{circ}} = 0$ by definition.

For the baseline ($\eta_3 = 0$), both the signal and control pairs exhibit V_{circ} values near the measurement floor

across the measured n range. This suggests that the dispersion observed at $\eta_3 > 0$ is driven by the injected 3-local terms rather than by native device residues; characterizing native diagonal anomalies is left for future work. As η_3 increases, the signal pair shows progressively larger dispersion: the $\eta_3 = 0.1$ and $\eta_3 = 0.2$ curves separate clearly from the baseline, with the latter reaching the highest dispersion values. The control pair (1, 4)—available only for $n \geq 5$ due to heavy-hex coupling constraints—remains near the floor regardless of η_3 , consistent with its exclusion from 3-local injection. This differential response—signal rising with η_3 , control flat—mirrors the simulation trend (Fig. 3) and is consistent with injected weight-3 content as the dominant source of dispersion.

Hardware error bars are 95% shot-bootstrap confidence intervals. Potential systematic effects such as multi-setting drift are addressed via interleaved scheduling and the paired signal-control design, with additional robustness checks reported in Appendices B and A. The full n -sweep evidence is provided by simulation (Fig. 3); the QPU data confirm that the effect survives device noise.

Panel B reports the phasor quality diagnostic amp_{\min} . Values remain high for both pairs across all measured configurations, consistent with the simulation quality checks (Section IV B).

C. Scalar summaries versus full profiles on hardware

Figure 5 established that κ -profile dispersion grows with η_3 for the signal pair on hardware. We now examine whether this growth is visible in the context-collapsed scalar $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ or only in the full profile, echoing the simulation analysis of Fig. 4.

Figure 6 displays the complete κ -profile at $n = 7$ for both signal and control pairs across the η_3 sweep. Each panel plots $\hat{\kappa}(z_{\text{rest}})$ for all 32 spectator contexts, with the scalar summary $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ shown as a horizontal dotted line and the profile spread (q_{10} – q_{90}) indicated by a right-margin bar. The phasor quality amp_{\min} is overlaid on the right axis.

The pattern mirrors the simulation finding. For the signal pair, $\hat{\kappa}^{\text{eff}}$ remains nearly constant across $\eta_3 \in \{0, 0.1, 0.2\}$, yet the profile fluctuations grow visibly: the spread bar widens visibly from Panel A to Panel E. A context-collapsed scalar would suggest little has changed; the full profile reveals substantial context dependence. In contrast, the control pair (right column) maintains a flat profile throughout, with both the scalar and the spread remaining stable regardless of η_3 .

The hardware data thus reproduce the central simulation finding: scalar summaries mask context-dependent structure that the full κ -profile resolves. Sustained high amp_{\min} across all panels confirms adequate measurement quality throughout the sweep.

Drift-robustness analyses, including scheduling com-

parisons and day-to-day repeatability, are provided in Appendices A and B.

VI. DISCUSSION

The preceding sections demonstrated that κ -profiles resolve context-dependent diagonal cross-effects in simulation, with the same scalar-versus-profile contrast corroborated on hardware. The inject-and-detect validation strategy follows standard QCVV practice—randomized benchmarking, cycle benchmarking, and robust phase estimation were each validated under controlled noise before characterizing native errors [13, 35, 36]—and extending to native higher-order residues is a natural next step (Section VID). We now compare this diagnostic with existing protocols, discuss scalability, outline applications, and summarize limitations.

A. Comparison with Standard Protocols

Quantum characterization protocols span a broad range, from coarse aggregate diagnostics to full reconstructions. Table I summarizes representative examples in terms of scope, output, and qualitative experimental overhead.

a. Full reconstruction methods. Quantum state tomography (QST), quantum process tomography (QPT), and gate set tomography (GST) aim at complete descriptions of states or processes.[17–19, 26, 37] These protocols provide complete information (e.g., density matrices or process models), but the number of parameters and measurement settings scales exponentially with system size, limiting feasibility beyond small systems. GST improves robustness by treating state preparation and measurement as unknowns to be characterized while yielding a predictive model.[19, 20] However, GST typically requires thousands of circuits and is most commonly applied to one- to two-qubit gate sets.[37, 38]

b. Scalar benchmarks. Randomized benchmarking (RB) and related protocols report aggregate metrics such as average error rates with substantially lower experimental overhead than tomography.[13, 14, 39] These protocols intentionally average over circuit- and context-dependent structure, producing compact figures of merit that are well-suited to scalable health checks. Standard RB analysis assumes time-independent noise; temporal correlations can induce deviations from simple exponential decay and complicate interpretation of finite-sample averages.[40, 41] Interleaved RB extends the framework to per-gate metrics, and cycle benchmarking (CB) characterizes entire layers in context, providing sensitivity to certain crosstalk effects.[35, 42] Despite these advances, RB-family outputs are aggregate fidelities and do not directly report the structure of coherent errors (e.g., distinguishing an unintended ZZ coupling from an over-rotation or depolarization).[43, 44]

TABLE I. **Comparison of κ -profiles with representative QCVV protocols.** κ -profiles provide context-resolved diagnostics for Z -diagonal unitaries. The trade-off is restricted scope (diagonal only) and profile-level diagnosis (flatness vs. non-flatness) rather than full parameter identification.

Protocol family	Scope	Output	Overhead ^a	Trade-offs
Randomized benchmarking (RB)	Diagnostic	Coarse figures of merit (e.g., average error rate)	Low	Scalable; limited structural insight.
Robust phase estimation (RPE)	Targeted parameter	Specific parameter(s) at high precision	Low ^b	Highly informative but narrow scope.
κ -profiles (this work)	Context-resolved diagnostic	κ -profile per pair; dispersion summaries	Low–Mod. ^c	Z -diagonal only; diagnosis, not identification.
Hamiltonian learning	Model-based reconstruction	Parameters of assumed Hamiltonian	Mod.–High	Predictive model; tailored experiments needed.
QST / QPT	Full reconstruction	Full density/process matrix	High	Maximally informative; scales poorly.
Gate set tomography (GST)	Full gate-set reconstruction	Self-consistent gate-set model	High	Detailed but circuit-heavy.

^a Qualitative proxy based on distinct circuits/settings.

^b Few settings, but circuit depth may dominate runtime.

^c Circuit count: $4MP$ for M contexts and P pairs.

c. Intermediate methods. Between aggregate benchmarks and full reconstruction, several protocols provide partial structural information with additional assumptions. Hamiltonian learning estimates coupling parameters within an assumed model; under locality constraints, recent results show sample complexity that can be independent of system size for finite-range interactions.[11] Robust phase estimation (RPE) targets specific gate parameters at high precision with relatively few circuit families, but its target is narrow (a small set of angles rather than a context-resolved diagnostic).[36, 45] Average gate fidelities from RB-style experiments can also be leveraged for sample-efficient reconstruction of multi-qubit unitaries via compressed sensing under structural assumptions such as approximate unitarity.[46] More general crosstalk detection protocols test conditional dependencies without fitting a complete process model.[5, 12, 47]

d. κ -profiles. κ -profiles target spectator-dependent phase structure in Z -diagonal unitaries by reporting a context-resolved curvature $\kappa_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}})$ for a chosen qubit pair.

The distinction from the crosstalk-detection tools cited above is one of output granularity. Context-dependence tests return a binary verdict and a scalar measure of distributional distance (e.g., total-variation distance or Jensen–Shannon divergence)[5]; crosstalk-detection protocols go further by *localizing* which region pairs interact, outputting a dependency graph whose edges are annotated with distributional distances[12]. In both cases the context variable is an externally imposed experimental condition (time period, neighbor driving, or region-level circuit setting), and the output does not retain a per-spectator-configuration functional form. The κ -profile

instead treats each spectator bitstring z_{rest} as the context variable and retains the *functional form* of the dependence: the curvature at each spectator configuration reflects the spectator-parity structure of higher-weight diagonal terms (Section II B), so the profile shape itself carries structural information—specifically, which spectator configurations shift the nonlocal phase and by how much—that a binary detection statistic does not preserve. This additional resolution comes at the cost of restricted scope: κ -profiles apply only to Z -diagonal unitaries (or unitaries rotatable to diagonal form by known single-qubit Cliffords), whereas general-purpose detection tools are model-free.

As established in Section II B, a strictly 2-local diagonal generator implies a flat κ -profile for every pair, whereas non-flatness is consistent with weight- ≥ 3 diagonal terms that include the measured pair (subject to the caveats in Section VI D). Within a layered QCVV workflow, dispersion scans from κ -profiles can prioritize qubit pairs for more resource-intensive follow-up methods (e.g., Hamiltonian learning or GST) when context dependence is indicated.[29] Indeed, Ref. [12] identifies the characterization of crosstalk-error *form*—beyond detection and localization—as an open problem; κ -profiles address one slice of this problem for Z -diagonal unitaries by providing the spectator-resolved functional shape that detection protocols compress away.

B. Scalability

The experiments in Sections IV and V enumerated all 2^{n-2} spectator contexts exhaustively, which was feasible

at $n \leq 7$ (at most 32 contexts). For P measured pairs and M spectator contexts, the four-setting readout requires $4MP$ distinct circuits and $4MPN$ total shots (N shots per circuit); however, exhaustive enumeration does not scale: at $n = 12$ there are $2^{10} = 1024$ contexts per pair, and at $n = 20$ the context space is larger by a factor of 2^8 .

This limitation is not fundamental to the κ -profile framework. Random sampling of M contexts from the full set of 2^{n-2} possibilities yields a consistent estimator of the circular dispersion V_{circ} . As noted in Section III C, the variance of this estimator scales as $O(1/M)$, independent of n . The statistical precision therefore depends on the sampling budget M , not on the size of the underlying context space.

As an illustration, in a 50-qubit system exhaustive enumeration would require $2^{48} \approx 10^{14}$ contexts. In contrast, sampling $M = 200$ uniformly random contexts, each measured with the four-setting protocol, uses $4 \times 200 = 800$ circuits for a single pair. If the κ -profile is flat (as predicted by strictly 2-local diagonal structure), sampled values cluster around the mean, yielding small estimated dispersion; if weight- ≥ 3 terms contribute to κ_{ij} , sampled values exhibit spread and the dispersion estimate increases.

The circular dispersion $V_{\text{circ}} = 1 - \bar{R}$, where \bar{R} is the mean resultant length of the phasor sample, is a standard estimator in circular statistics with concentration properties that support confidence-interval construction.[31, 32] For M independent samples from any distribution on the circle, the sample mean resultant length \hat{R} converges to the population value at rate $O(1/\sqrt{M})$, and confidence intervals can be obtained by bootstrap or analytic approximations.[31–34, 48] Comparable sample sizes (e.g., 50–100 random sequences) are often sufficient for tight confidence bounds on aggregate metrics in randomized benchmarking.[13, 49] The same statistical principles support dispersion estimation from moderate M without exhaustive enumeration.

Overall, the sampling-based design makes the measurement overhead scale with the desired statistical precision rather than with qubit count.

C. Applications

The results in Sections IV and V establish detectability of injected higher-order diagonal terms under controlled conditions. Relating κ -profile anomalies to application-level performance is beyond the scope of this work, but context-dependent diagonal structure is relevant in several settings.

a. Variational algorithms. QAOA cost Hamiltonians and hardware-efficient VQE ansätze frequently rely on Z -diagonal phase structure, where coherent systematic errors can accumulate across layers.[6–9] In this regime, κ -profiles provide pair-resolved evidence for whether the effective two-qubit phase depends on spec-

tator configurations, complementing context-averaged scalar benchmarks.

b. Hamiltonian simulation. Trotterized simulation decomposes time evolution into repeated diagonal layers, and coherent per-step phase errors accumulate linearly with circuit depth.[10] κ -profiles test whether these diagonal phase interactions exhibit spectator dependence that would be averaged out by scalar metrics.

c. Quantum error correction. Syndrome extraction circuits contain diagonal gates whose phase errors can introduce correlated faults between data and ancilla qubits, challenging independent-error assumptions.[5, 12] κ -profiles can localize qubit pairs whose effective diagonal interactions vary with spectator state, providing diagnostic information relevant to correlated phase mechanisms.

d. Compiler and scheduler validation. Crosstalk-aware scheduling can reduce error rates in structured circuits.[24, 29] Tracking κ -profile dispersion across compiler or scheduler changes provides a regression signal for context-dependent diagonal effects without requiring full tomographic reconstruction.

e. Platform generalization. The present formulation targets Z -diagonal unitaries, a common setting for superconducting devices.[3, 50] When the target unitary is diagonal in the X or Y eigenbasis, a global single-qubit Clifford rotation maps it to a Z -diagonal form.[26] This basis flexibility makes the diagnostic relevant to platforms with multi-body couplings expressed in other Pauli bases, including trapped-ion systems where three- and four-body interactions have been realized.

D. Limitations

Several limitations constrain the scope and interpretation of κ -profile diagnostics.

a. Diagonal scope. The method targets Z -diagonal unitaries (operators diagonal in the computational basis). Near-diagonal unitaries, which contain small off-diagonal coherent errors in addition to diagonal phases, lie outside the current framework. Extending the diagnostic to detect or bound off-diagonal leakage remains future work.

b. Drift sensitivity. The four-setting phasor readout combines expectation values from separate circuit executions. If the effective measurement frame drifts between settings, the curvature estimate acquires a bias that does not vanish with increased shot count.[28] As discussed in Section III D, interleaved scheduling reduces this bias by ensuring that all settings experience similar drift within each randomized cycle, but it does not eliminate the effect entirely. The paired signal-control design and day-to-day repeatability checks (Appendix B) provide additional safeguards. The phasor-quality diagnostic amp_{min} is reported alongside all curvature estimates; degraded amp_{min} indicates reduced interference contrast and increased uncertainty in $\hat{\kappa}$. More general temporally correlated (non-Markovian) dynamics can be described within multi-time frameworks such as process tensors,[51]

but reconstructing such memory structure is beyond the scope of the present diagnostic.

c. Diagnostic signal, not identification. A non-flat κ -profile indicates context-dependent diagonal structure consistent with weight- ≥ 3 terms involving the measured pair, but it does not uniquely identify the responsible interaction. Multiple distinct Hamiltonian configurations can produce similar profile shapes, and experimental artifacts—including residual SPAM errors or unmodeled drift—can also contribute to apparent non-flatness. The method is therefore most naturally interpreted as a screening diagnostic that flags pairs for follow-up, not as a standalone identification procedure.

d. Sampling coverage. When contexts are sampled rather than exhaustively enumerated (Section VIB), rare or localized non-flatness may be missed if sampling density is insufficient. The dispersion estimate V_{circ} reflects the average spread across sampled contexts; a single anomalous context among many flat ones could be diluted below detectability. For cases where specific spectator configurations are suspected, stratified or adaptive sampling may be preferable to uniform random sampling.

e. Hardware corroboration only. The QPU experiments in Section V demonstrate that the scalar-versus-profile contrast observed in simulation is observable on physical hardware, but no quantitative model matching is claimed. The injected η_3 parameter defines a controlled model family, not a calibrated device parameter (see Section III). Characterizing native higher-order diagonal residues (anomalies present at $\eta_3 = 0$) remains future work; the near-floor dispersion observed for both signal and control pairs at $\eta_3 = 0$ suggests that any such native effects are below the current detection threshold or measurement noise floor.

VII. CONCLUSION

Scalar benchmarks for Z -diagonal unitaries intentionally average over spectator configurations, collapsing context-dependent phase structure into a single number. The κ -profile framework developed here recovers this structure: a gauge-invariant plaquette curvature[21, 22] is estimated for each qubit pair and spectator context via a four-setting phasor readout requiring only single-qubit Cliffords[26] and Z -basis measurement. We proved that purely 2-local diagonal generators yield flat profiles, and that weight- ≥ 3 terms involving the diagnostic pair can break this flatness. Simulations ($n = 2-7$) and IBM QPU experiments[23, 25] corroborated that profile dispersion tracks injected higher-order content while context-collapsed scalars remain nearly unchanged. Overall, κ -profiles provide a low-overhead diagnostic that reveals context-dependent diagonal cross-effects hidden to scalar screening.[13, 29] Several directions remain open. The current framework targets unitaries that are exactly Z -diagonal; extending the diagnostic to near-diagonal cases—where small off-diagonal coherent errors

coexist with diagonal phases—would broaden applicability but requires bounding or detecting such leakage. On the experimental side, the QPU results presented here inject controlled 3-local content via the residue-injection knob η_3 ; characterizing whether any native higher-order residues at $\eta_3 = 0$ exceed the current noise floor is a natural next step toward using κ -profiles for anomaly discovery rather than validation alone. Integration with error mitigation pipelines, where κ -profile dispersion could inform which pairs benefit from targeted phase correction, offers another avenue for practical deployment. The sampling-based design ensures the method scales to future large-scale quantum systems without fundamental modification: measurement overhead is determined by the desired statistical precision rather than qubit count, and the readout demonstrated here at $n = 7$ generalizes directly to 100-qubit or 1000-qubit processors.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data and code that support the findings of this article are openly available at Ref. [52].

Appendix A: Scheduling robustness check

a. Motivation. Because the four-setting readout combines expectation values from separate circuit executions, time-dependent drift can introduce a bias in $\hat{\kappa}$ via the mechanism described in Section III D.[28] Our default hardware workflow uses *interleaved* scheduling (the four settings appear in a fixed repeating cycle) as a precaution; here we explicitly test whether the reported κ -profile dispersion is sensitive to this choice.

b. Experimental design. We use the $\eta_3 = 0$ (baseline) instance on `ibm_fez`[23, 24] at $n = 7$, and measure both the signal pair (0, 1) and the the control pair (1, 4). We compare two scheduling strategies. In the *interleaved* mode, four separate segments I_1-I_4 were each executed with 512 shots per circuit; the circuit list is ordered by context and pair, and for each (context, pair) the four settings are executed in a fixed cyclic order (I_1-I_2 precede the blocked segment and I_3-I_4 follow it, as indicated in Fig. 7). In the *blocked* mode, a single dataset B with 2048 shots per circuit was collected, where all circuits for a given setting are executed together before moving to the next; this corresponds to four consecutive execution phases, one per setting, that are then reassembled into a single counts dataset. The $I_1-I_2 \rightarrow B \rightarrow I_3-I_4$

FIG. 7. **Scheduling robustness check** ($\eta_3 = 0$, $n = 7$) on `ibm_fez`. Signal pair (0,1) and the control pair (1,4) measured using interleaved scheduling (I_1 – I_4 , 512 shots per circuit each) and blocked-by-setting scheduling (B , 2048 shots per circuit; shaded). The pooled estimate I_{sum} combines the raw counts from I_1 – I_4 to form a shot-matched interleaved dataset (2048 shots per circuit), and is not an additional run. Vertical boundaries mark the interleaved \rightarrow blocked \rightarrow interleaved transitions. (A) κ -profile dispersion V_{circ} for each dataset. (B) Phasor-quality diagnostic summarized by amp_{min} over contexts. Points show bootstrap medians; error bars denote 95% shot-bootstrap confidence intervals obtained by per-circuit binomial resampling of the raw counts (5000 resamples).

ordering places the blocked segment centrally in time to symmetrize slow drift.

To separate scheduling effects from shot-count effects, we additionally form a shot-matched interleaved dataset I_{sum} by pooling the raw counts from I_1 – I_4 at the per-circuit level (yielding 2048 shots per circuit); I_{sum} is not an additional run. All datasets use identical circuits, so the comparison isolates execution ordering.

c. Observation. Figure 7 shows that the blocked schedule B and the shot-matched interleaved estimate I_{sum} yield comparable V_{circ} [31, 32] for both the signal and control pairs, while amp_{min} remains stable across schedules. The larger dispersion observed in the individual 512-shot interleaved segments I_1 – I_4 is consistent with increased finite-shot variability and collapses upon pooling to I_{sum} . Overall, within shot-bootstrap

uncertainty[33, 34] we observe no material dependence of V_{circ} on whether the four settings are interleaved or blocked. We therefore retain interleaved ordering as a default precaution in hardware sessions where multi-setting drift may be larger, while treating this check as evidence that the reported dispersion trends are not an artifact of a particular scheduling choice.

Appendix B: Day-to-day repeatability

As a further drift-robustness check beyond the scheduling comparison in Appendix A, we test day-to-day repeatability under a fixed physical layout.[28]

FIG. 8. **Day-to-day repeatability at fixed layout (QPU, $n = 7$)**. Two independent `ibm_fez` sessions (Day 1 and Day 2) repeat the same $n = 7$ η_3 sweep for the signal pair (0,1) and control pair (1,4) using the same circuit set and interleaved scheduling. (A) Paired dispersion contrast $\Delta V_{\text{circ}} = V_{\text{circ}}(\text{sig}) - V_{\text{circ}}(\text{ctl})$ versus η_3 ; error bars are 95% shot-bootstrap confidence intervals. (B) Phasor quality amp_{min} for each pair; points show the mean across spectator contexts and whiskers extend to the 10th percentile across contexts. The η_3 -dependent increase in ΔV_{circ} is consistent across days while amp_{min} remains high, making a single-run drift explanation unlikely.

We repeat the $n = 7$ hardware experiment on `ibm_fez` in two independent sessions (Day 1 and Day 2), using

the same compilation choices, the same spectator-context enumeration (all $2^{n-2} = 32$ contexts), and the same shot budget ($N = 2048$ shots per circuit). We focus on the signal pair $(0, 1)$, which is targeted by the injected weight-3 terms in our residue-injection family, and the control pair $(1, 4)$, which is connected on the device but excluded from 3-local injection and therefore serves as a role-matched control (Section VB).

To summarize repeatability in a drift-robust manner, we report the paired contrast between signal (sig) and control (ctl)[31, 32],

$$\Delta V_{\text{circ}} := V_{\text{circ}}(\text{sig}) - V_{\text{circ}}(\text{ctl}), \quad (\text{B1})$$

with uncertainty obtained from shot-level bootstrap resampling of raw measurement counts (performed in a paired fashion across the simultaneously measured signal and control data).[33, 34] Figure 8A shows that ΔV_{circ} exhibits the same qualitative η_3 -dependent trend on both days: it remains near the floor at $\eta_3 = 0$ and increases monotonically for $\eta_3 > 0$, reaching the largest values at $\eta_3 = 0.2$. The consistent η_3 trend across independent days makes a single-run drift event an unlikely explanation for the observed dispersion increase.

Figure 8B reports the phasor-quality diagnostic amp_{min} for both pairs across the same sweep. amp_{min} remains high for both signal and control on both days, indicating that the dispersion trends in Panel A are not driven by a collapse in interference contrast. Taken together, these observations support the conservative interpretation used throughout the paper: the hardware data corroborate that the injected context-dependent diagonal structure produces an observable, repeatable increase in κ -profile dispersion, without claiming quantitative model matching to an underlying device model.

Appendix C: Protocol derivation

This appendix derives the ideal identities in Eq. (12), namely that the four circuit settings in Fig. 2 return $m_{0,0} = \cos a$, $m_{0,1} = \sin a$, $m_{1,0} = \cos b$, and $m_{1,1} = \sin b$ for the phase differences $a := \phi(z^{00}) - \phi(z^{01})$ and $b := \phi(z^{10}) - \phi(z^{11})$ introduced in Sec. IID. Throughout, we assume an ideal Z -diagonal unitary $U = \text{diag}(e^{i\phi(z)})$ and noiseless state preparation and measurement.

a. Setup: restricting an n -qubit diagonal to a two-qubit plaquette. Fix a diagnostic pair (i, j) and a spectator context $z_{\text{rest}} \in \{0, 1\}^{n-2}$, prepared as a computational basis state $|z_{\text{rest}}\rangle$ on all qubits except i, j . As in Sec. IIB, let $z^{ab} \equiv z^{ab}(z_{\text{rest}})$ denote the n -bit string with $(z_i, z_j) = (a, b)$ and spectators equal to z_{rest} . For this fixed context we define the four diagonal phases

$$\phi_{ab} := \phi(z^{ab}), \quad (a, b) \in \{0, 1\}^2, \quad (\text{C1})$$

and the associated phase differences

$$\begin{aligned} a &:= \phi_{00} - \phi_{01}, & b &:= \phi_{10} - \phi_{11}, \\ \kappa &= a - b \equiv \phi_{00} + \phi_{11} - \phi_{01} - \phi_{10} \pmod{2\pi}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C2})$$

Operationally, fixing (z_{rest}, z_i) reduces the action of U on qubit j to a *single-qubit* relative phase between the two basis states that differ only in z_j .

b. Equatorial readout identity. Consider an equatorial single-qubit state

$$|+\theta\rangle := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + e^{i\theta}|1\rangle). \quad (\text{C3})$$

A direct calculation gives

$$\langle X \rangle_{+\theta} = \cos \theta, \quad \langle Y \rangle_{+\theta} = \sin \theta. \quad (\text{C4})$$

In our circuits we always perform a Z -basis measurement after a final Hadamard on qubit j , so the reported quantity

$$m_{x,s} := \langle Z_j \rangle_{\text{after final } H_j} \quad (\text{C5})$$

is equivalently an X -basis expectation on the state *before* the final Hadamard, since $HZH = X$. Thus it suffices to track the equatorial phase θ acquired by qubit j and apply Eq. (C4).[26, 30]

c. Circuit parametrization. In Sec. IID the four settings are indexed by $(x, s) \in \{0, 1\}^2$:

- x selects whether qubit i is prepared in $|0\rangle$ ($x = 0$) or $|1\rangle$ ($x = 1$), implemented as X^x on i .
- s selects whether qubit j is prepared in $|+\rangle$ ($s = 0$) or $|+i\rangle$ ($s = 1$), implemented as H followed by an optional S on j :

$$\begin{aligned} |+_s\rangle &:= S^s |+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + i^s |1\rangle), \\ s &\in \{0, 1\}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C6})$$

All spectator qubits are prepared in $|z_{\text{rest}}\rangle$. After applying U , we apply a final H on j and measure Z_j .

d. Derivation of the a settings: $x = 0$. For $x = 0$, qubit i is fixed to $|0\rangle$ and only qubit j is placed in a superposition. The prepared input state (including spectators) is

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_{0,s}^{\text{in}}\rangle &= |z_{\text{rest}}\rangle \otimes |0\rangle_i \otimes |+_s\rangle_j \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|z^{00}\rangle + i^s |z^{01}\rangle). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C7})$$

Since U is diagonal, it only attaches phases:

$$\begin{aligned} U |\Psi_{0,s}^{\text{in}}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(e^{i\phi_{00}} |z^{00}\rangle + i^s e^{i\phi_{01}} |z^{01}\rangle) \\ &= e^{i\phi_{00}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|z^{00}\rangle + e^{i(\phi_{01} - \phi_{00} + s\pi/2)} |z^{01}\rangle). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C8})$$

The global phase $e^{i\phi_{00}}$ is irrelevant. Because the spectators and qubit i remain in the same computational basis state across both branches, the post- U state is a product

of a fixed register state and an equatorial state on qubit j with relative phase

$$\theta_a(s) = \phi_{01} - \phi_{00} + s\frac{\pi}{2} = -a + s\frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (\text{C9})$$

As noted above, measuring Z_j after the final Hadamard is equivalent to measuring X_j before it. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} m_{0,s} &= \langle X_j \rangle_{+\theta_a(s)} = \cos(\theta_a(s)) \\ &= \cos\left(-a + s\frac{\pi}{2}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C10})$$

Evaluating the two cases gives the desired identities:

$$m_{0,0} = \cos a, \quad m_{0,1} = \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - a\right) = \sin a. \quad (\text{C11})$$

e. Derivation of the b settings: $x = 1$. For $x = 1$, we instead fix qubit i to $|1\rangle$, so the two branches differ between $|z^{10}\rangle$ and $|z^{11}\rangle$. The same computation yields

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_{1,s}^{\text{in}}\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\left(|z^{10}\rangle + i^s|z^{11}\rangle\right), \\ U|\Psi_{1,s}^{\text{in}}\rangle &= e^{i\phi_{10}}\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\left(|z^{10}\rangle \right. \\ &\quad \left. + e^{i(\phi_{11}-\phi_{10}+s\pi/2)}|z^{11}\rangle\right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C12})$$

The relative phase on qubit j is now

$$\theta_b(s) = \phi_{11} - \phi_{10} + s\frac{\pi}{2} = -b + s\frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (\text{C13})$$

and the measured expectation is

$$m_{1,s} = \langle X_j \rangle_{+\theta_b(s)} = \cos\left(-b + s\frac{\pi}{2}\right). \quad (\text{C14})$$

Thus

$$m_{1,0} = \cos b, \quad m_{1,1} = \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - b\right) = \sin b, \quad (\text{C15})$$

completing the derivation of Eq. (12).

f. Phasor estimator and an equivalent closed form. Combining Eqs. (C11)–(C15), the phasors defined in Eq. (13) satisfy (ideally)

$$\begin{aligned} u_a &= m_{0,0} + i m_{0,1} = \cos a + i \sin a = e^{ia}, \\ u_b &= m_{1,0} + i m_{1,1} = \cos b + i \sin b = e^{ib}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C16})$$

Hence

$$u_a \bar{u}_b = e^{i(a-b)} = e^{i\kappa}, \quad (\text{C17})$$

and the estimator $\hat{\kappa}_{ij}(z_{\text{rest}}) = \text{Arg}(u_a \bar{u}_b)$ in Eq. (14) returns the plaquette curvature modulo 2π . [21, 22]

For completeness, expanding $u_a \bar{u}_b$ in terms of the measured real numbers $m_{x,s}$ gives an equivalent ‘‘closed-form’’ pair of identities:

$$\begin{aligned} u_a \bar{u}_b &= (m_{0,0}m_{1,0} + m_{0,1}m_{1,1}) \\ &\quad + i(m_{0,1}m_{1,0} - m_{0,0}m_{1,1}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C18})$$

so that $\cos \kappa$ and $\sin \kappa$ can be obtained directly as the real and imaginary parts in the noiseless limit. In practice

we use the argument-based estimator of Eq. (14), which remains well-defined even when intermediate phases wrap by 2π .

Appendix D: Four-setting circuit details

Figure 9 expands the circuit diagram of Fig. 2 by showing all four settings explicitly. The bit x toggles the preparation of qubit i between $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, while the bit s selects the X or Y measurement axis for qubit j via an S gate. [26, 30] Spectator qubits (the remaining $n-2$ qubits initialized to a fixed z_{rest} configuration) are omitted for clarity. Appendix C derives the noiseless expectation values and the resulting estimator.

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

FIG. 9. **Four-setting phasor κ readout: explicit circuits.** Panels (A–D) correspond to settings $(x, s) \in \{0, 1\}^2$. Each circuit yields $m_{x,s} = \langle Z_j \rangle$; the phasors $u_a = m_{0,0} + im_{0,1}$ and $u_b = m_{1,0} + im_{1,1}$ give $\hat{\kappa} = \text{Arg}(u_a \bar{u}_b)$ with quality diagnostic $\text{amp}_{\text{min}} = \min(|u_a|, |u_b|)$.

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